

Agricultural Strategies at Dja'de el-Mughara, Northern Syria (10th - 9th millennium cal. BC)

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Résumé

Vers 12 000 av. n. è., au Proche-Orient, se mettent en place de profondes mutations, qui, sur près de cinq millénaires, permettent l'émergence des premières sociétés sédentaires. L'économie de subsistance, jusqu'alors caractérisée par la cueillette et la chasse, repose progressivement sur la culture des plantes et sur l'élevage. Ces changements s'observent sur le site de Dja'de el-mughara (Syrie du Nord) dont l'occupation, depuis la seconde moitié du 10^{ème} millénaire (fin du PPNA) jusqu'à la seconde moitié du 9^{ème} millénaire (PPNB ancien), permet de mieux comprendre l'évolution des pratiques agricoles durant la néolithisation. Cet article présente les résultats préliminaires d'une étude qui associe l'analyse archéobotanique des macrorestes végétaux et l'analyse fonctionnelle des outils de moisson. L'outillage provenant des niveaux les plus anciens de Dja'de étant actuellement conservé en Syrie, l'analyse fonctionnelle ne porte que sur le matériel de la phase récente (DJ3). La confrontation de ces deux approches dresse néanmoins un premier aperçu de l'évolution des stratégies agricoles dans l'une des premières communautés villageoises du Proche-Orient. L'identification des végétaux exploités par les habitants permet d'aborder leur éventuelle utilisation à des fins domestiques.

L'étude de près de quatre cents échantillons archéobotaniques ne montre aucun indice de domestication morphologique des plantes à Dja'de. Toutefois, l'augmentation de la fréquence des céréales et des légumineuses au cours de l'occupation du site, conjuguée à celle des mauvaises herbes arables, laisse envisager la pratique de la culture, et non plus seulement de la cueillette, comme moyen de subsistance. Par ailleurs, l'analyse fonctionnelle d'une centaine de lames lustrées permet de comprendre la manière dont les villageois ont exploité les ressources végétales disponibles dans leur environnement, en particulier les céréales, durant le processus de domestication.

Mots-clefs : Néolithisation ; Syrie ; Dja'de el-mughara ; agriculture ; économie végétale ; analyse archéobotanique ; analyse fonctionnelle ; moisson ; éléments de faucille.

Abstract

In Southwest Asia, the numerous mutations that have taken place around 12000 cal BC resulted in the emergence of the first sedentary societies. Hunting and gathering were progressively replaced by plant cultivation and animal husbandry as a new form of subsistence. Those changes can be observed at Dja'de el-Mughara (Northern Syria), occupied for a long time from the 10th millennium (late PPNA) to the end of the 9th millennium cal. B.C (early PPNB). The site highlights the evolution of agricultural practices during this period, also characterised by many social and technological changes. This paper aims to present some preliminary results from both archaeobotanical study and functional analysis of harvesting tools. Due to the syrian conflict, most of the lithic pieces were inaccessible, thus the functional analysis was only carried on the material from the late phase (DJ3). This work provides an insight into the evolution of agricultural strategies at one of the earliest sedentary communities. The identified taxa allow us to discuss their probable use in daily life activities.

The study of more than 400 archaeobotanical samples shows that there is no evidence for morphological domestication. However, the increase of frequencies of cereals and pulses with time, associated to that of arable weeds, let consider that inhabitants of Dja'de were cultivators and not only collectors or gatherers. The functional analysis of a hundred glossy blades from Dja'de allow to understand the way neolithic groups exploited the plant resources in their environment (especially cereal harvesting) during the process of plant domestication.

Keywords : Neolithisation ; Syria ; Dja'de el-mughara ; Agriculture ; Plant Economy ; Archaeobotanical Analysis ; Functional Analysis ; Harvesting ; Sickle Blades.

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1. Introduction

The 11th-9th millennia cal. B.C is a key period for subsistence change in Southwest Asia since practices evolve from acquisition (hunting, gathering and collecting) to production (animal husbandry and cultivation; AURENCHE & KOZLOWSKI, 1999; TANNO & WILLCOX, 2006; WILLCOX & TANNO, 2006; WILLCOX *et al.*, 2008a; CAUVIN, 2010). During this period, we observe an increasing number of (semi)-permanent settlements presenting preliminary signs of agriculture (WILLCOX, 1996, 1999; STORDEUR & WILLCOX, 2009; WILLCOX & STORDEUR, 2012) like the recovery of higher quantities of cultivars (mainly cereals and pulses), the reduction of wild plants and some changes in seeds morphologies (WILLCOX, 2004). The archaeobotanical study carried on aceramic neolithic sites give insights into the large diversity of plants exploited by the inhabitants. The functional analysis conducted on lithic tools offers a good opportunity to grasp plant exploitation modalities.

1.1. The site of Dja'de el-mughara

Dja'de el-mughara is located in northern Syria on the western bank of the Euphrates river (Figure 1). The tell has been excavated by É. Coqueugniot between 1991 and 2010 (COQUEUGNIOT, 1998; COQUEUGNIOT, 2014), in the context of the permanent mission of El Kowm-Mureybet, and as part of the international rescue project linked to the construction of the Tishreen flood barrier on the Middle Eu-

phrates. However, due to its high topographic position, the tell was preserved from the rising river even after the impoundment of the dam. Excavations stopped in autumn 2010, and were resumed in 2011 because of the Syrian civil war.

The deep stratigraphy, based on several soundings (Figure 2), suggests that the small village (around 1,5 ha) was occupied from the final PPNA (9310 cal. BC) to the early PPNB (8290 cal. B.C). The site was abandoned around 8200 cal. B.C. It was inhabited again during the Pre-Halaf period (beginning of the 6th millennium B.C) and during the Early Bronze (3rd millennium BC).

1.1.1. The natural environment

The village was situated on the middle quaternary terrace (Q_{II} Pleistocene terrace) on the left bank of the Euphrates in the south east corner of the close to the Jezireh (BESANÇON & GEYER, 1996; COQUEUGNIOT, 1998; BELMONT, 1999). This formation consists of gravels and pebbles of metamorphic rocks from the Taurus mountains and consolidated there in a type of conglomerate that preserves the tell from lateral erosion exerted by the Euphrates (COQUEUGNIOT, 1998). The high position of the site, located 15m above the alluvial plain, protected it from the violent floods regularly caused by the Euphrates river (COQUEUGNIOT, 1998).

The site is situated in the area where annual rainfall are between 250 and 300 millimeters (Figure 1). The alluvial plain, compri-

Fig. 1: Situation of the neolithic site of Dja'de in Northern Syria (DAO C. Douché).

sing the main river and occasional meanders forming vegetalised islands with poplars and tamarisks, constituted a rich ecological niche (ROITEL, 1997; COQUEUGNIOT, 1998; HELMER *et al.*, 1998; WILLCOX *et al.*, 2008b). The banks of the Euphrates and the quaternary terraces spreading layers of the river's left bank were also sources of lithic raw material, including flint pebbles (COQUEUGNIOT, 1994a). Furthermore, resources like wild fauna (gazelles; GOURICHON & HELMER, 2004),

plants (oriental terebinth, almond trees and wild cereals), lithic raw materials (basalt and flint) were also found in the Jezireh (COQUEUGNIOT, 1998). Thus, complementarity of resources available in the local environment provided a favorable natural surrounding for a (semi-) permanent type of habitat. This might explain the longevity of the occupation of the site from the final PPNA to the early PPNB, corresponding to approximately one millennium.

1.1.2. The occupation

The neolithic occupation was divided in three main phases according to the architecture and the lithic technology (COQUEUGNIOT, 2014).

The earliest phase, “*Dja'de 1*” (9310-8830 cal. B.C.), corresponds to the final PPNA. The domestic architecture is characterised by small rectangular and circular units with tiled floors and walls made of mud and large stones (COQUEUGNIOT, 2014). Lighter structures were al-

Fig. 2: Localisation of the soundings areas on the archaeological site (DAO C. Douché from G. Devilder).

so discovered on the edge of the tell. Apart from domestic structures, the main discovery from this period is the “Painting Building”, a subcircular and half-buried construction with exceptional dimensions (internal diameter close to 7.50 meters) whose some walls are covered with black, white and red geometric patterns (COQUEUGNIOT, 2014). This building reminds the “community buildings” of Mureybet, Jerf-el-Ahmar and Tell’ Abr (STORDEUR *et al.*, 2000; YARTAH, 2004). For this phase, burial deposits were rare (CHAMEL, 2014). The lithic industry is essentially laminar with unipolar and some bipolar knapping (ARIMURA, 2007). The major tools are scrapers and laminar tools include arrowheads, drills, burins and glossy blades (ARIMURA, 2007).

The phase “*Dja’de 2*” (8800-8500 cal. B.C) corresponds to the beginning of the early PPNB. Actually, this phase is only discovered at *Dja’de*. Rectangular houses often composed by several large cells (7 m x 2,5 m) represent the domestic architecture and several grill-plans structures were identified in open-areas (COQUEUGNIOT, 2014). In the “E sounding”, layers composed by numerous animal bones mixed with charcoals were interpreted as remaining of feasts (GOURICHON & HELMER, 2004; COQUEUGNIOT, 2014). Collective graves were often related to architecture whereas isolated bone remains were mainly found in open areas (CHAMEL, 2014). Bipolar laminar knapping is oriented towards obtaining straight and regular blades extracted from various types of cores among them naviform cores are considered as cultural markers of PPNB period (COQUEUGNIOT, 1994b; ARIMURA, 2007). Among them, endscrapers type are still major tool, As-

wad arrowheads and blades with “*ergot*” are also characteristic features.

The phase “*Dja’de 3*” (8540 - 8290 cal. B.C) corresponds to the second part of the early PPNB. Contemporary levels were discovered at Mureybet IV_A (CAUVIN, 1977 and Cheikh Hassan (ABBÈS, 2002) but these were flooded by the Euphrates following the construction of the dam of Taqba. The domestic architecture is characterised by rectangular buildings with mud walls and stone framework, smaller than the previous phase and often single-celled. Grill-plans are still present. A collective grave (« *Maison des morts* ») delivered about 80 skeletons, buried as primary and secondary inhumations located near or inside the cells (CHAMEL, 2014). The lithic industry is based essentially on a bipolar laminar knapping made with soft stone hammer and using a fine grain flint (COQUEUGNIOT, 1994a; ARIMURA, 2007). Among the tools, Byblos arrowheads, blades with “*ergot*” and glossy blades are characteristic elements.

Thus, this transition period, from PPNA to PPNB, is marked by many social and technological changes and agriculture is one of them.

1.2. Problematic

The PPNA (9500-8700 cal. B.C) is characterized by cultivation of morphologically wild plants (cereals and pulses). The presence of arable weeds, the increase in seed size, the mul-

tiplication of storage places³, sickle blades and grinding stones on many sites in the Levant (COLLEDGE, 2001; WILLCOX, 2004; WILLCOX *et al.*, 2008a) suggest the relative intensification of practices. From the Middle PPNB (7500-7000 cal. B.C), the first evidences of morphological domestication of cereals appear. Some researchers (HILLMAN & DAVIES, 1990) have also underlined the significant role of sickles blades in crop domestication, which may have operating an involuntary selection of grain with solid rachis (mutant specimens present in tiny proportion among wild cereals). Sowing this seeds would have led to the morphological domestication. From the Late PPNB (7500-7000 cal. B.C), agricultural practices are clearly set up with a large part of domestic cereals.

The aim of this paper is to highlight the agricultural strategies at Dja'de el-mughara, a key site in understanding the process of neolithisation, since its occupation, which stands on the eve of morphological domestication of cereals, is contemporary of the proto-agriculture step (WILLCOX, 2008; STORDEUR & WILLCOX, 2009; STORDEUR & WILLCOX, 2012; YARTAH, 2004). The main questions raised are : which types of plants were exploited by the inhabitants and how (i.e. gathered or cultivated) ? What is the 'position' of Dja'de regarding the domestication process ? Which harvesting technics were used ? And, finally, how these plants were used in the domestic space ?

1.3. Material and method

In order to answer such questions, we combined two complementary approaches : archaeobotanical study of macroscopic charred remains and functional analysis of "glossy blades" .

1.3.1. The archaeobotanical study

During the 20 years of excavations, thick ashy layers were observed and systematic sampling was carried out. Samples were taken from diverse archaeological contexts like hearths, pits, occupation and demolition layers as well as burials.

Charred remains were recovered using the flotation method with a 0.5 mm mesh. 227 samples were studied as part of European project and published by G. Willcox (WILLCOX, 1996). The study was then extended and detailed as a part of a PhD, mainly by giving greater consideration of archaeological contexts and chronology. Sorting was led using a Nikon SM 645 and identifications relied on reference collections and atlases of the Archéorient Institute (Jalès) and those of the National Museum of Natural History (Paris). A minimum number of individuals (MNI) have been estimated by counting and converting the total number of fragments according to categories (1/2, 1/4 of a complete specimen).

3. As the possible round granaries discovered at Dhra' in Jordan (KUIJT & FINLAYSON, 2009; KUIJT, 2009). Even if the function of those buildings as granaries is not clear (due to the absence of grain), the amount of grains recovered on archaeological sites increases, showing a more efficient collect or a better production.

1.3.2. The functional analysis

According to methodological protocols established by S. Semenov and L. Keeley (SEME NOV, 1964; KEELEY, 1980), the aim of the functional analysis is to reconstitute the function of tools from the macro- and microscopic study of use-wear traces (micropolish, striations, edge-rounding and edge-removals). On the working edge, the organisation of these use-wear traces depends on the activity made with the tool. For interpreting them, it is necessary to refer to an experimental collection of tools whose function is known by the researcher.

The type of tools studying here was selected from a functional character : the presence, on blades, of a typical macroscopic « gloss » traditionally associated to the collect of siliceous soft plants, and particularly in the context of the Neolithic to cereal harvesting (ANDERSON-GERFAUD, 1988; ANDERSON, 1991 ; ANDERSON, 1992; ANDERSON, 1998; KOROBKOVA, 1993; UNGER-HAMILTON, 1988; UNGER-HAMILTON, 1989; UNGER-HAMILTON, 1991). Indeed, among the lithic tools from Near eastern Neolithic sites, the glossy blades are common. Their increase in the lithic industries, correlated with the in-

crease of cereals in the subsistence economy of the Neolithic groups, led people to associate the « gloss » to cereals harvesting (CAUVIN, 1983). However, we have to mention that this macroscopic criterion is insufficient to consistently interpret the « glossy blades » as sickles blades : the work of another siliceous soft plants — and even that of various wet raw materials — also produce a macroscopic gloss on the working edge (ANDERSON, 1991; ANDERSON, 1992; ANDERSON-GERFAUD *et al.*, 1991; CAUVIN, 1983); CAUVIN & COQUEUGNIOT, 1985; JENSEN, 1994; KOROBKOVA, 1993; VAUGHAN, 1985). That is why, recognising the function of the « glossy blades » and identifying sickles blades requires to resort the methods of functional analysis.

We analysed 96 glossy blades coming from Dja'de 3⁴. This sample was collected by É. Coqueugniot during the excavations and brought to France to document harvesting technics used at Dja'de. The observations were made with a Perfex Science macroscopic binocular (magnification 45x) and an Olympus BHM metallographic microscope (magnification 100x, 200x, 400x). The interpretations were based on comparisons made with tools

4. The number of glossy blades considered here is less important than that given in a previous publication because we preferred to exclude those whose stratigraphic context was disturbed by more recent levels (PICHON, 2017a)

5. Cereal harvesting was carried out near Séranon in the Alpes-Maritimes in France. During these experiments, curved and straight sickles implemented with flint blades were used to cut semi-green and ripe domestic emmer wheat (*T. subsp. monococcum*). In order to complete our experimental collection, cutting of yellow and green reeds was realised in the Northern France (PICHON, 2017a)

6. The study of the archaeological tools required comparisons with experimental tools, which may have been used to collect plants in similar environmental conditions (climate, soil dryness, maturity of plants). So, we consulted the experimental collection of P. Anderson, which contains blades used to harvest green and half-green wild cereals (*T. dicoccoides*, *Hordeum spontaneum*, *T. boeoticum* subsp. *thaoudar*) from Jebel Druze in Syria, half-green wild cultivated cereals from Jalès (*T. boeoticum* subsp. *thaoudar*), to cut green and yellow reeds

from personal experimentations⁵ and from P. Anderson's experimental collections⁶.

The observations made of these experimental blades allowed us to recognise the diagnostic characters — such as the morphology, the topography and the extent of the micropolish, the presence of striations, the degree of edge-

removals (JENSEN 1994) — of cutting cereals, reeds and grasses.

Despite a chronological study of plant remains evolution, the confrontation of these two approaches only concerns the last occupation phase (Dja'de 3). This is due to the limited access to lithic industry, mainly stored in Syria, and that is not available.

(*Phragmites communis*) and various grasses (ANDERSON-GERFAUD *et al.*, 1991; ANDERSON, 1998; ANDERSON, 2000

2. Archaeobotanical study : results from Dja'de 1 to 3 (C. Douché)

In total, 281 samples from levels dated to the PPN periods were analysed, which corresponds to 50419 items (Figure 3). The ar-

chaebotanical study shows important quantities of fruits (1799 remains (NR)) among which we found oriental terebinth (*Pistacia* sp.), ca-

Fig. 3: a. *Secale* sp. grains, b. *Secale* sp. spiklet bases, wild type (smooth scars), c. *Secale* sp. spiklet bases, domestic type (tied rachis), d. *Hordeum vulgare* sp. grains, e. *Lens* sp. seeds, f. Papaveraceae seeds, g. *Adonis* sp. seeds.

per seeds (*Capparis* sp.), figs achenes (*Ficus* cf. *carica*) and some almonds nutshells (*Prunus*/*Amygdalus* sp.). We have to mention that some fruits, like caper and figs, provide numerous seeds. So, in order to reduce that bias, we calculated the number of individuals (NMI), based on the number of seed per fruit.

We observe that oriental terebinth is the main taxa encountered at Dja'de, which reflects the steppic environment surrounding the site. A large proportion of cereals, grains (6619 items) and chaff (1499 items) remains, were identified. Glume wheats (emmer and einkorn wheats), hulled barley and rye remains were recovered. Ubiquity percentages (number of samples in which a taxa is present) show that barley is the most common taxa, through all occupation levels (present in *ca.* 80% of samples; Figure 4). Rye is the second most important cereal, and grains ubiquity increases between the beginning and the end of the occupation. Finally, einkorn and emmer wheat grains are present in low quantity but their ubiquity increase through time.

Grasses are annual plants, which means that in the wild, when plant are ripe, they diffuse seeds (ear shatter and spikelet bases fall down on the ground), grains germinate and come to fruiting the following year. The gene causing the smooth abscission at maturity was turned off that lead to facilitate the cultivation. For domestic cereals, even when they are ripe, ears do not shatter and threshing is required to break up the ears. This shattering way according to wild or domestic type is more or less

visible on the archaeological material : roughly, the shattering scar is straight and smooth for wild (brittle rachis) and rough (or damaged) for domestic cereals (Table 1).

Chaff remains analysis, indicate that the morphology of cereals is of wild type. Even if some domestic types spikelets were identified, their quantity is insignificant (5%) compared to wild type which represents 95% .

Apart from cereals, archaeobotanical samples delivered some pulses (Figure 5). We found peas (*Pisum* sp.), bitter vetches (*Vicia ervilia*), faba beans (*Vicia faba*), and few chickpeas (*Cicer* sp.), but the most important seed is the lentil (*Lens* sp.). Seeds are present in approximately 80% of samples from the three phases, often in huge quantities.

The domestication process of pulses is only visible for peas. But unfortunately, the preservation of the *testa* from archaeological peas of Dja'de was not good enough to determine their status⁷. Nonetheless, the huge quantities and the size of lentils seeds suggest the possibility of their cultivation.

Finally, a broad-spectrum of wild plants were identified among the numerous macroremains recovered from Dja'de (Figure 6). Although few have been identified to the specie level, most of them could be considered as arable weeds (i.e. plants growing in disturbed habitats, especially fields). We encountered Poaceae family plants such as *Bromus* sp., *Eremopyrum* sp., *Lolium* sp., *Stipa* sp., and *Taeniatherum* sp.. Most of such wild taxa present an increasing ubiquity from the ear-

7. Few peas seem to present a testa with a rough texture, potential evidence of wild specimen.

Fig. 4: Cereal grains ubiquity in % (number of samples in which the taxa is present). DJ1 : 60 samples, DJ2 : 65 samples, DJ3 : 156 samples.

liest to the latest period. These plants probably come from the steppic area. Small Legumes such as *Astragalus* sp. or *Medicago* sp. and a large variety of very small seeds (*Hyoscyamus* sp., *Glaucium* sp., *Silene* sp.) were also identified in quite important quantities. They might have been imported in the village as weeds of

cultivated plants, by the wind (as they are very light) or by animals.

Wild barley stands are still visible in the local environment of the site. Wild einkorn is found farther north near the Turkish border while wild rye only grows considerably farther north at high altitudes (for example in the Ka-

1) Wild specimens	2) Domestic specimens
Scar surface : smooth and straight steep orientation	Scar surface : rough, damaged or internodes remained attached (sometimes smooth)
Ventral surface of internode straight	
Curve below the scar surface, more or less marked	Curve below the scar surface, well pronounced and adjacent
	Torn tissues on the lower part of the scar
	Lower part of the scar protrude from the scar
Upper abscission scar not affected by charring	Scar morphology affected by charring : torn tissues in the lower part of the scar are bent
Maximum internode thickness : 0.72 - 1.29mm	Maximum internode thickness : 0.56 - 1.04mm
1) Scar Orientation < 100°	Scar orientation > 100°

Tab. 1: Table showing the different morphological criteria used in archaeobotany in order to differentiate wild and domesticated emmer wheat spikelets (based on TANNO & WILLCOX, 2012; WEIDE *et al.*, 2015).

Fig. 5: Pulses ubiquity in % (number of samples in which the taxa is present). DJ1 : 60 samples, DJ2 : 65 samples, DJ3 : 156 samples.

raça Dağ mountains) and probably represent a degraded landscape from the Neolithic period, as testified by their importance in archaeobotanical assemblages. The predominance of barley in crop assemblages might reflect the ecological conditions around Dja'de because such plant is well tolerant to arid conditions and poor chalk soils.

The presence of rye during the Neolithic period is interesting because this cereal doesn't grow in the local environment today. This taxa was identified on several aceramic neolithic sites in the Middle Euphrates area as at Abu Hureyra (grains) (HILLMAN, 2000; HILLMAN *et al.*, 2001), Tell Mureybet (impressions; WILLCOX, 2008, Jerf el-Ahmar (grains and chaff; STORDEUR & WILLCOX, 2009; STORDEUR & WILLCOX, 2012) and Tell Abr' 3 (grains; WILLCOX, 2009; YARTAH, 2013). Some argue that rye disappeared from the

region around the Middle PPNB (WILLCOX, 2008; WILLCOX *et al.*, 2008a) due to the onset of warm and dry Holocene climate. Hillman and colleagues found grains and chaff in the Konya Basin, at the Middle-Late PPNB site of Can Hassan III (FRENCH *et al.*, 1972; HILLMAN, 1978), but this could be the result of the climatic gradient since the site is located in an area where mean annual rainfall are around 400-600 mm/year.

The increase of wild - potentially arable weeds - plants, through the time might correspond to the intensification of cultivation (WILLCOX, 2012; SNIR *et al.*, 2015). Comparing their height with crops, highlights the presence of small wild plants which could indicate a cut in the lower part of the cereal stems.

Based on archaeobotanical remains, it appears that plants exploited by the inhabitants of Dja'de were still morphologically wild

Fig. 6: Wild plants (possible arable weeds) ubiquity in % (number of samples in which the taxa is present). DJ1 : 60 samples, DJ2 : 65 samples, DJ3 : 156 samples.

(smooth rachis). Nonetheless, according to the ubiquity and morphology (grains well developed) of crops and weeds, it seems that a cultivation process was established.

The low cut of cereals and the recovery of many chaff remains testify the complex and integrated system of agriculture : grains were

probably used for human consumption ; chaff might have been used as fuel (the use as fodder is unlikely since all animals exploited - mostly gazelles, hares, aurochs and birds - were wild and hunted) and straw may have been used in architecture (particularly rye which produces long and strong stems).

3. Functional analysis : results from Dja'de 3 (F. Pichon)

Traces on the blades present some common features related to the work of siliceous plants in a cutting motion (Figure 7). Traces are bi-facial and covering (more than 1 mm), often macroscopic.

The polish texture is generally smooth and reflectivity is bright to very bright. Numerous longitudinal and parallel striations indicate the one way motion of the tools. Cutting edge are completely rounded and covered by the polish

Fig. 7: Archaeological traces related to the work of siliceous plants in a cutting motion and interpreted as cereals harvesting (up) and reeds cutting (down).

and often retouched or resharpened, so that the scars are difficult to identify.

Variations observed in these use-wear traces, in term of degree of polish development (linkage and intrusion) and polish topography, are probably dependant in the length and intensity of work (JENSEN, 1994). But some subtle variations are also related to the type of siliceous plants, *i.e.* grasses, reeds or cereals, which have been cut with these blades. Experimental data have indeed shown that some traits, related to variation in polish topography and polish texture and directional features, appear to be exclusive to certains plants and can be observed in archaeological context (Jensen, 1994). Degree of intrusion and presence/absence of scars are also really helpful as diagnostic elements of contact material (JENSEN, 1994).

Thus, use-wear created by the harvest of cereals is less bright and smooth than use-wear from cutting reed and polish topography is generally rather flat than domed (ANDERSON-GERFAUD, 1983; VAUGHAN, 1985; UNGER-HAMILTON, 1988; VAN GIJN, 1989; JENSEN, 1994). Moreover, polishes from cutting reeds may be present some linear depressions which give it a fluted or rippled topography (JENSEN, 1994). The traces are also more intrusive for the cereals than those from reeds or grasses. For the reeds, the polish is evenly distributed over the high points of the immediate edge and the first part of the interior area (JENSEN, 1994; for the grasses, the polish, which is smooth and domed, is limited along the immediate edge (VAN GIJN, 1989; JENSEN, 1994). Striations and fluted polish topography are not

diagnostic feature of cutting grasses (VAN GIJN, 1989; JENSEN, 1994).

Based on these significant elements of comparison, we propose that 84 items were used for harvesting cereals (96 active areas; Figure 7a). The others were probably used for cutting siliceous plant material harder than cereals (11 items with 12 active area; Figure 7b) and other kind of soft but undetermined siliceous plant (1 item with 2 active areas).

- The *sickles blades* are mainly obtained from bipolar knapping (80%), whereas the others are undermined (19%) or unipolar (0,01%). Central blades are preferred (57%) but lateral blades are also well represented (30%). Selected blades are regular : they present a plane face (rare curvatures are due to the convexity of the preserved bulb), and straight profile. The width are between 9, 88 and 23,31 mm (average : 15,54 mm +/-2,98) and the thickness are between 2,15 and 8,05 mm (average : 4,61 mm +/-1,10). The lengths of the preserved sickles blades are between 22,76 and 142,94 mm, (average : 59,18 mm +/- 25,45), but essentially concentrated between 30 and 60 mm. The standard deviation shows a significant dispersion of the values around the average, explained by the presence of long and whole blades and by a proximal blade fragment of 90 mm in length. In general, the lengths of conserved sickle blades segments are between 30 and 60 mm. In the Northern Levant, at Mureybet, sickle blades are between 40 and 60 mm in length and 10 and 15 mm in width during the PPNA (phase III_A;

CAUVIN, 1978, p. 68; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ URQUIJO & A, 2008, p. 378) and get closer to those of Dja'de 3 during the EPPNB (phase IV_A; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ URQUIJO & A, 2008, p. 401). At Jerf el-Ahmar, during the PPNA, strong blades, 50 to 60 mm long and 10 to 13 mm wide, are used as sickles (STORDEUR & ABBÈS, 2002, p. 580). During the transition phase (recent Mureybetian), their dimensions are even more important : the blades are 60 mm in length and 15 mm in width (STORDEUR & ABBÈS, 2002, p. 580). During the MPPNB, at Halula, sickle blades are between 50 and 90 mm in length (BORRELL & MOLIST, 2007, p. 62). This phenomenon of enlargement of the blades is general and all the tools, including sickle blades, follow this trend.

Cutting edges are in most cases retouched (73% of the active areas) and functional study showed that these retouches took place during the use for resharpening the edges (60% of the retouched areas) (PICHON, 2017*a*; PICHON, 2017*b*). On 12 blades, the distribution of use-wear shows that the two edges have been used for harvesting and for at least 7 of them, edges were resharpening.

The in-band distribution of the polish and the presence of black-brown residues on some blades show that the blades were inserted in a parallel way in a handle and maintained by mastic, probably bitumen (Figure 8).

Their relatively short dimensions let us consider them as « sickle elements » (CAUVIN, 1983) aligned one after the other to form a continuous cutting edge. The polish is often more intense and invasive on the central part of the blades while it is more limited or totally absent on their extremities (Figure 9). Thus, the central part of the cutting edge being exposed the most with the worked material, which is consistent with a curved haft. On some blades, this hypothesis is also confirmed by the retouch of the opposite cutting edge and/or of the extremities and which give them a slightly curved morphology adapted to the handle. These elements evokes the parallel insertion of the sickle blades into a curved handle, process attested in other neolithic sites of the Middle Euphrates such as at Mureybet IV_A during the EPPNB and at Halula during the Middle and Recent PPNB (IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1998; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ URQUIJO & A, 2008; BORRELL & MOLIST, 2007). The appearance of curved sickles, which differ from epipalaeolithic straight sickles, seems to reflect an intensification of agricultural practices at this time. Improving the gesture and the rhythm of the harvester, it represents crucial evolution in harvesting techniques (IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1998, p. 134; ASTRUC *et al.*, 2012, p. 685).

Some variability on the degree of striation and the topography, more

or less flat, of the polish were observed (Figure 10; PICHON, 2017a). Regarding the experimental context (UNGER-HAMILTON, 1989; ANDERSON, 1991; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1998; IBÁÑEZ *et al.*, 2014), this kind of variations is depending on the intensity of use, on the height of the harvest (the lower is the cutting, the more abrasive particles are between the blades and the stems, the more stria-

ted is the micropolish) and on the humidity of the stems (the dryer are the stems, the more abraded and flatter is the polish).

Fluctuations in the modalities of the harvest at Dja'de, linked to these factors, could explain the variations of the archaeological use-wear traces (PICHON, 2017a).

It lets consider a certain level of technical complexity for the same activity with,

Fig. 8: Preserved brown adhesive residue, probably bitumen, on a sickle blade from Dja'de 3 (Picture F. Pichon).

8. Since the conference, another hypothesis, based on confocal microscopy, has been proposed to explain this variability in Dja'de and the general evolution of harvest traces during the neolithisation in the Levant (IBÁÑEZ *et al.*, 2014; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ *et al.*, 2016; PICHON, 2017b). Between 12,000 and 5,000 BP, polish become more flat, striated, abraded and less shiny (for example : ANDERSON, 1992; UNGER-HAMILTON, 1992; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1998). Through experimentations, these variations have been linked with new economic behaviours, such as cereal cultivation. Experiments have shown that the harvest of wild cereals should be made before the full maturity of the ears to prevent excessive loss of grains, while the harvest of domestic

Fig. 9: Polish distribution (in grey) on the sickle blades suggesting the parallel insertion of the blades in a curved handle (Drawing by F. Pichon).

perhaps, the practice of harvesting at different cutting heights and at inhomogeneous maturity stages of the cereals⁸.

- The blades used for cutting harder siliceous plants are not very different from the sickle blades both in knapping technique (mostly bipolar central blades) as in morphology (average width : $15,99 \pm 4,51$; average thickness : $4,58 \pm 0,94$; average length of 6 complete tools : $56,95 \pm 21,22$). Only one blade present traces on both edges. Like observed on the sickle blades, black-brown residues of adhesive are present showing that they were certainly used hafted, but without possible reconstruction. These blades could be used to cut aquatic species growing in the alluvial plain, like reeds (*Phragmites communis*) (ROI-

TEL, 1997, p. 103). This kind of activity with flint blades is indeed documented in other epipalaeolithic and neolithic levantine sites as Hatoula (ANDERSON, 1994, p. 281), Hayonim (ANDERSON & VALLA, 1996), Aswad (ANDERSON, 1995, p. 224), Abu Hureyra and Mureybet (ANDERSON, 1992, p. 201; (IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ URQUIJO & A, 2008, p. 401). Finally, the blade used for cutting undetermined soft siliceous plant (grasses?) is really different from the others. This is a long blade (123,11 mm in length, 17,76 mm in width and 7,40 mm in thickness) with proximal laterals and opposite notches, used on both edges. The traces do not extend to this retouched part, which seems to be the prehensile part.

grain occurs when the ears are ripe. However, the polish from harvesting green cereals are more domed and shiny as those related to the harvest of ripe cereals. So, the evolution of traces have been linked to the degree of moisture present on the stems, and by hypothesis, connected to the domestication process

Micropolish of two different sickles blades from Dja'de (x100). The micropolish is bright and smooth. It presents a domed topography with a reticular «smelted snow» appearance. We observe few striations on this type of micropolish.

Micropolish of two different sickles blades from Dja'de (x100). The micropolish is covering, bright and smooth. It presents a generally domed topography but in certain areas the topography tends to be more flat. Comet-shaped pits and longitudinal striations give the way of the unidirectional movement and suggest that the stems were cut near the ground.

Micropolish of two different sickles blades from Dja'de (x100). The micropolish is very covering but less bright than previously. It appears also more flat and more abraded with numerous irregular micropits. Longitudinal striations give the way of the unidirectional movement and suggest that the stems were cut near the ground.

Fig. 10: Archaeological polish interpreted from harvesting cereals : variations in degree of striations and in the topography of the micropolish (domed to flat) (Pictures by F. Pichon). The raw material is a fine-grained flint.

4. Discussion

The combination of results from archaeobotanical and functional analysis highlights the exploitation of Poaceae (including reeds, *Phragmites* sp.) by the neolithic inhabitants of Dja'de. The reed importance was already shown by the charcoal analysis led by V. Roitel (ROITEL, 1997). At Dja'de, as most of the sites situated on the edge of the Euphrate river (WILLCOX *et al.*, 2008c), the villagers knew how to take advantage of the ecosystems diversity supplying both by the riparian forest (in particular reeds) and the steppic area (Poaceae but also oriental terebinth and almonds that were collected around the site). The acquisition of those plants can be related to various uses, as raw material like fuel and litter as well as worked like food (human and animal), architecture (wattle-fence, roof) or basketry (mats, containers; STORDEUR, 1989). About that, ethnographic materials suggest a wide range of uses in the domestic space for those plants, which is not necessarily found in the archaeological records (i.e. plaited crafts; ERTUŽ, 2006).

The discovery of many cereal grains and chaff remains (barley, rye and glume wheats) suggests their use as the main food base. Although cereals are still of wild type, their increased frequency through the occupation period of the site in parallel with that of arable weed plants probably indicates the setting up of the first agricultural strategies. Dja'de is a part of the global dawn of farming process, observed in the whole Near East (WILLCOX, 2014; COLLEDGE, 2001; COLLEDGE & CO-

NOLLY, 2006; CONOLLY *et al.*, 2011). The variations observed on the sickles-blades from Dja'de (see below) have been already observed on the epipalaeolithic and neolithic sickles from the Near East : the micropolish are more intensively developed and become flatter and more abraded during the neolithisation (UNGER-HAMILTON, 1991; ANDERSON, 1992; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1998). These developments have been linked to the maturity of the seeds at the time of the harvest (green or ripe) and thus were related to the necessary changes in harvesting techniques in the crop domestication (UNGER-HAMILTON, 1989; ANDERSON, 1991; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ, J.-J. AND GONZÁLEZ *et al.*, 1998). At Dja'de, these variations could also be related to this process : this issue is actually studied with confocal analysis applied to sickle blades from Dja'de (IBÁÑEZ *et al.*, 2014).

Grasses may have been collected for different purposes than food supplies. Some observations like the striated micropolish as well as the presence of weed plants with a small height in the archaeobotanical assemblages indicate that some sickle blades were used to harvest close to the ground in order to recover the stalks. If, we know that chaff material is used as tempering in *leben* at Dja'de (Figure 11) like in the other aceramic sites in the Euphrates (STORDEUR & WILLCOX, 2009), we can also consider that the straw, as well as the stalks of reeds, may have been used in the domestic space such as components of the architecture.

Fig. 11: Impressions of chaff and grains in *leben* (Picture by É. Coqueugnot).

Indeed, some ethnoarchaeological researches, like the work of F. Z. Ertuğ about basket work craft in Turkey (ERTUĞ, 2006), show that the building construction with wickerwork or woven twig is still visible in some Anatolian villages : stems are used making some fences (especially for animals). The same study also show that the reeds screens are used by the nomads of Southeast Anatolia as partitions walls in tents, wind breaks around the tents and as sheep pens. This type of plants can be used to build roofs. For example, rye has high and strong stems adapted to such application (i.e. north European thatched roofs ; NOLAN *et al.*, 2015). Roof coverings have a

differential longevity according to the grasses type used : reed roof can survive between 50-100 years whereas rye or wheat roofs have to be repaired very 20-35 years (BERGE, 2009). Finally, leaves or stems of cereals and reeds can also be used to make some mats : this tradition was important in Anatolia as floor coverings and for the construction of the ceilings of mud-roofed houses (ERTUĞ, 2006).

Fig. 12: Preserved phytolithic skeleton mats lying on a floor from Dja'de (Picture by É. Coqueugnot).

At Dja'de, woven mats were identified during the excavation (Figure 12). They were preserved thanks to their high content in siliceous (phytoliths) and their analysis show that it might be related to reed plants (*Phragmites* or *Typha* sp.)⁹. They were probably used to cover the floors - the geomorphological study shows that vegetation covers recovered some occupation floors in Dja'de (HOURANI, 1993) - or al-

9. Willcox, personal communication

so to envelop the deceased bodies (i.e. kind of shroud) as suggested by remains of a mat in the “*Maison des morts*” (CHAMEL, 2014). Finally, leaves and stems (i.e. reeds, rye) can be also used for basketry to make some containers, which one can easily imagine the utility in a sedentary agricultural community. The presence of transversal use-wear traces related to scraping of siliceous soft plants (like reeds) on some other tools from Dja'de could be a witness to this type of activity.

At Dja'de, one of the excavation areas light buildings (huts or tents) were unearthed (COQUEUGNIOT, 2014: study made by M.-A. Courty) and layers showing occupation and abandonment phases, which could refer to a seasonal village occupation (COQUEUGNIOT, 2014).

According to building materials, we can imagine that regular raw material acquisition

was necessary to make some reconstructions and repairs.

For example, the winter rains probably had consequences/took its toll on roofs and walls. The inhabitants of Dja'de needed thus easily accessible and renewable material organic (BELMONT, 1999).

But, grasses (i.e. reeds and cereals stems) are annuals : they complete their life-cycle in one year and they reach maturity around the end of spring/beginning of summer. They were widely available in the local environment (the alluvial plain and the steppic area) of the site every year. In this context, the preferential choice of this light construction material seems rational, whereas wood material was probably less abundant (partly due to a longer reproduction cycle), required a woodland management and was likely used for architectural structures (mostly posts) (BELMONT, 1999).

Conclusion

As presented above, it seems that every year, around the beginning of May, according to the well development of cereal caryopsis (barley). (before grasses maturity and grains spread on the ground), the group harvested wild cereals with sickles with a low cut, then separated grains, chaff and stalks, repaired old and built new structures and finally lived there (cooking, hunting, making mats).

The use-wear analysis lead on harvesting tools presents marks corresponding to the harvest of cereals with such humidity in their stem suggesting that they may have been cut before their maturity (green or semi-green). This hypothesis feats well with the observations made on plant remains (particularly spikelets) presenting the characteristics of wild morphologies. Indeed, experiments showed that to be efficient (least grain spillage of germinable grain), wild cereals should to be cut in a green state and wild cultivated cereals in a semi-green state (ANDERSON, 1991; IBÁÑEZ ESTÉVEZ *et al.*, 2016).

Cultivation practices seem testified by the presence of arable weeds identified in archaeobotanical samples. As already mentioned, arable weeds grow in disturbed habitats, especially fields where cultivation practices (like ploughing, irrigation) were made. More the practices are intensive ; more such type of invasive plants is developed. We noted that arable weeds increased through the occupation of the

site, meaning that agricultural practices were intensified.

According to archaeozoological data, people were hunting during the winter season. Based on archaeobotanical data, they were managing cereals and pulses during spring and thanks to use-wear analysis we might say that they were harvesting before maturity, at the end of spring. Finally, archaeological discoveries show that people were using by-products for domestic activities during the following period.

In the long term, and if the political situation allows a return to the Syrian terrain, it will be envisaged to complete this first multidisciplinary approach by studying the glossy blades coming from Dja'de 1 and 2.

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